

LARGE STRAIN FLOW CURVE IDENTIFICATION FOR SHEET METAL

by

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ABSTRACT

The large strain flow curve is an essential input for the calibration of a myriad of plasticity models required for accurately simulating sheet metal forming processes and the mechanical performance of formed components. Studies on large strain flow curve identification can be divided in three main categories. The first class of experiments generate statically determinate stress states which unambiguously correlate analytically to the external load and measured strains, hence enable a direct measurement of the large strain flow curve. The second category relies on the intermittently measured flow stress using pre-strained samples to construct the large strain flow curve. The third category consists of methods that minimize the discrepancy between the experimentally acquired and the numerically computed measurand to inversely identify a chosen hardening law representing the large strain flow curve. The paper presents an overview of the state-of-the-art methods to acquire the large strain flow curve of sheet metal. A selected number of methods are reviewed and recent developments are discussed in detail. Finally, an objective assessment of the selected methods is pursued by applying them to a DP600 steel sheet.

KEYWORDS

Large strain flow curve; in-plane torsion test; post-necking tensile test, plane strain compression test, hydraulic bulge test

1 INTRODUCTION

A fundamental convention in the theory of continuum plasticity states that the plastic work resulting from a multiaxial stress and strain state can be computed from the product of an equivalent stress and an increment of the equivalent plastic strain. This equivalent stress-equivalent plastic strain curve represents the work hardening serving as an important input for the calibration of a myriad of plasticity models for sheet metal. Conventionally, the stress-strain curve obtained from a uniaxial tensile test in the Rolling Direction (RD) is used for this purpose. The standard tensile test requires minor experimental effort. The limitation of the standard tensile test is that it is confined to determining the work hardening up to the point of maximum uniform tensile strain. Yet, many sheet forming processes involve plastic deformations well beyond the attainable strain in a standard tensile test. This maximum strain is due to a structural instability rather than a material failure. To cope with this, it is common practice to estimate the post-necking work hardening behaviour by extrapolating the pre-necking work hardening behaviour. However, extrapolation strongly depends on the adopted hardening law. Such uncertainty clearly biases the calibration of plasticity models (anisotropic yield functions, anisotropic hardenings models, damage models, theoretical Forming Limit Diagrams (FLD), crystal plasticity models, fatigue life predictions of formed components, etc.). These models are extensively used to predict forming defects (e. g. wrinkling and fracture), product properties (e.g. spring-back, residual stresses, damage level and hardness) and product performance (e. g. fatigue life formed components). A comprehensive discussion on the influence of extrapolated strain hardening behaviour on the construction of Marciniak-Kuczynski (M-K) based forming limit diagrams, for example, is given in Mohammadi et al. (2014).

Figure 1. Methods to characterize the large strain flow curve of sheet metal.

Although this problem of extrapolation is well known, it is difficult to experimentally acquire post-necking strain hardening behaviour. Currently, the studies on large strain flow curve identification can be divided in three main categories (see **Figure 1** for a schematic overview). The material tests in *Category 1* adopt a carefully designed, yet often simple geometry, enabling to probe the work hardening beyond the maximum uniform tensile strain. The key point is that these material tests generate statically determinate stress states which unambiguously correlate analytically to the external load and measured strains. The hydraulic bulge test is a good example: at the top of the dome, a quasi-balanced biaxial tensile stress state prevails throughout the entire experiment. The stress state can be analytically determined using the pressure, radius of curvature and current thickness at the apex. This enables us to measure the flow curve beyond the maximum uniform tensile strain. Other examples belonging to this category are: Bridgman's method (Bridgman, 1952), the shear test (Rauch, 1992), the in-plane torsion test (Tekkaya et al., 1982), the plane strain compression test (Loveday et al., 2006), the stack compression test (Maeda et al., 1998), the multi-axial tube expansion test (Kuwabara and Sugawara, 2013) and the in-plane bending test (Naseem et al., 2020). It should be noted that the analytical approach inevitably comes with assumptions. For example, the simple shear test assumes a homogenous deformation throughout the measurement gauge (Bouvier et al., 2006). However, it is well known that the simple shear test cannot be "homogeneous" by the physics of the free boundaries. Material tests which involve friction (stack and plane strain compression) have a similar

concern with regard to the assumed uniform deformation. However, when properly executed, material tests from *Category 1* yield sufficiently accurate flow curves for engineering applications. Finally, each material test comes with a specific deformation mode. Consequently, due to potential plastic anisotropy of the metal sheet, a conversion based on the work equivalence principle of the acquired flow curve towards uniaxial tension in the RD is often required (ISO 16808 (2014) standard).

In *Category 2*, tensile testing of homogeneously pre-strained samples are used to construct the flow curve. The early work of Langford and Cohen (1969) exemplifies this approach: the wire drawing process is used to pre-strain the wire to a specific value of plastic strain. In the next step, the standard tensile test is used to determine the flow behavior. By conducting several experiments with different amounts of plastic strain, the large strain flow curve can be constructed. As concluded by Gil Sevillano et al. (1980), wire drawing and rolling are ideal candidates for this purpose because of the associated compressive stress states deferring structural damage up to large strains. The methodology relies on two fundamentals:

- a) The pre-straining process enables to establish conditions of homogeneous deformation. For example, in the case of wire drawing, Langford and Cohen (1969) as well as the other researchers assume homogenous properties over the cross-section of the wire, which can be a source of error.
- b) The mechanical tests used to measure the flow stress intermittently maintain the deformation process under the same conditions as in the pre-stretching process. The latter implies that for example rolled sheets should be intermittently tested using the plane-strain compression test. Moreover, the intermittent flow stress should be measured at the same strain rate.

Zhuang et al. (2013) recently proposed to homogeneously pre-strain sheet samples using cold rolling. In this work, the sheet properties are assumed to be constant over the thickness after rolling. In addition, the large strain flow curve was constructed by performing tensile tests. Zhuang et al. concluded that the approach can be used to obtain the large strain flow curve. Kolpak et al. (2021) used a forward extrusion process on metal sheets for homogenous pre-straining. Plastic pre-strains up to 1.6 are reached and the test allows the characterization of very thin sheets. In contrast to the other studies, Kolpak et al. used specimens after cold extrusion for testing that had a nearly homogeneous stress and strain state. Furthermore, probably the most important advantage of the method by Kolpak et al. is that the pre-straining is performed under exactly simple-tension deviatoric stress states so that the subsequent testing by

simple tension is not biased by anisotropic hardening effects. It is shown that after extrusion only a small core of the extrudate exhibits a nearly homogeneous stress/strain state and therefore the whole extrudate diameter cannot be used for testing. Due to the similarity in the deformation mechanics of wire drawing and extrusion a similar conclusion can be applied to wire drawing albeit here the inhomogeneity will be much smaller than in extrusion due to the relatively small drawing strain per pass. Other pre-straining methods are also proposed, e.g. Poulin et al. (2020) used the Continuous Bending under Tension (CBT) test (Emmens and van den Boogaard, A. H., 2009) to pre-strain tensile samples and construct the large strain flow curve.

The *category 3* consists of material tests for which one cannot analytically derive the stress and strain states from the measurands. The most popular approach here is to extract the work hardening from the diffuse neck of a tensile test, yet it can be applied to any experiment that probes large plastic deformations. For example, Gavrus et al. (1996) proposed an inverse analysis to identify the large strain behavior based on the torsion test. Capilla et al. (2017) successfully applied the in-plane stretch bending test to inversely determine the large strain flow curve of high-strength steel sheets. So-called inverse methods, e.g. finite element model updating (FEMU) techniques (Zhang et al., 2019), energy methods (Coppieters et al., 2011) and the virtual fields method (VFM) (Kim et al., 2013) are used for this purpose. Inverse methods basically minimize the difference between the experimentally acquired and numerically computed measurand (e. g. force, strain or stress field) or seek an energy balance by inverse determination of the chosen hardening law. The benefit is that strain hardening laws can be determined up to large plastic strains. The disadvantage is that the identification accuracy relies on the predictive accuracy of the selected hardening law. To cope with this, Rossi et al. (2018) and Denys et al. (2018) have explored the possibility to inversely identify a multi-linear hardening law using VFM and FEMU, respectively. Starman et al. (2019) proposed to use a cubic spline in the post-necking region.

This paper delivers firstly an overview of the state-of-the art methods from categories 1 and 3 to determine the large strain flow curve of sheet metal. Secondly, the paper aims at finding common ground by applying the selected methods to the same sheet metal. This approach allows for an objective comparison and assessment of the investigated approaches. The first section defines the term “large strain flow curve” and elaborates on the work hardening stages of metals. Section 2 embarks on the experimental methods to acquire the large strain flow curve of sheet metal. The focus in this section is on the methodology and the most recent state-of-the-art developments for each of the considered material test. Section 3 is devoted to the assessment

of the selected material tests. To this end, the material tests are applied to DP600 steel sheet.

2 LARGE STRAIN FLOW CURVE

Work hardening is caused by dislocation interaction processes and the aim of a work hardening theory is to predict the flow curve, i.e. strain hardening represented by the true stress and the true plastic strain. The use of a flow curve requires the availability of equivalence criteria for stresses and strains enabling to derive any complex deformation from a unique flow curve (Gil Sevillano et al., 1980), which is a material property:

$$\sigma_f = f(\bar{\epsilon}_p) \quad (1)$$

with σ_f the flow stress and $\bar{\epsilon}_p$ the equivalent plastic strain being scalars associated through equivalence criteria with the tensorial stress and strain (rate) states, respectively.

Here the dependency of the flow stress is solely confined to the equivalent plastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}_p$. However, in general the flow curve also depends on stress state, strain rate and temperature (Sung et al., 2010). It must be noted that when the strain hardening behavior cannot be accurately described by a single state variable, which is the equivalent plastic strain or similar (dislocation-density related), then the notion of (a unique) flow curve makes less sense. The flow curve for sheet metal is usually measured in the Rolling Direction (RD) of the metal sheet. Obviously, the function f in Eq. (1) is linked to micro-mechanical phenomena responsible for work hardening driven by a variety of microstructural parameters.

Strain hardening of polycrystals is typically divided into different stages. These stages are schematically shown in **Figure 2** by plotting the hardening rate θ as a function of the critical resolved shear stress τ :

$$\theta = \frac{d\tau}{d\Gamma} \quad (2)$$

with Γ the overall amount of dislocation slip representing the strain. As soon as yielding occurs in polycrystals, stage III hardening starts. For metals, the micro-mechanisms in stage III are well understood and a widely accepted model has been proposed by Kocks and Mecking (2003).

The latter model for stage III hardening reads as:

$$\theta = \theta_0 \left(1 - \frac{\tau}{\tau_{III}}\right) \quad (3)$$

with θ_0 the hardening rate at $\tau = 0$ and τ_{III} the saturation stress associated with stage III, respectively. This model can be converted using the Taylor factor into a flow curve, i.e. the classical Voce model:

$$\sigma_f = C(1 - me^{-K\bar{\epsilon}_p}) \quad (4)$$

with material constants C , m and K . For stage III hardening, the Voce model is a micro-mechanically based hardening model.

Figure 2. Schematic hardening stages: hardening coefficient versus flow stress slip, after Kocks and Mecking (2003).

The black open circles in **Figure 3** show the strain hardening of a low carbon steel sheet measured using a tensile test in the RD. The solid red curve is the Voce model (Eq. (4)) fitted to the data acquired using the standard tensile test. It can be inferred that the overall fitting quality is good, but a closer look shows that the model cannot accurately capture the initial yield stress and the strain hardening rate close to the point of maximum uniform strain. The latter is particularly of relevance when dealing with large deformations. Indeed, one can easily understand that extrapolation into the post-necking region (i.e. beyond maximum uniform strain) using the calibrated Voce law as shown in **Figure 3** will yield erroneous post-necking strain hardening behaviour. Voce's model is clearly not "flexible" enough to model this behaviour. A possibility that has been used to deal with this problem is the description of flow curves by successive equations, for example a two-stage Voce model (Coppieters et al., 2019):

$$\tau = \begin{cases} \tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{III}} - (\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{III}} - \tau_0) \exp\left(\frac{-\theta_0}{\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{III}} - \tau_0} \gamma\right) & \text{for } \gamma \leq \gamma_{\text{T}} \\ \tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{IV}} - (\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{IV}} - \tau_{\text{T}}) \exp\left(\frac{-\theta_{\text{T}}}{\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{IV}} - \tau_{\text{T}}} \gamma\right) & \text{for } \gamma > \gamma_{\text{T}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with

- τ_0 the initial flow stress in stage III;

- θ_0 and θ_T the initial hardening rate and the hardening rate at the transition point (i.e. γ_T) between stage III and stage IV, respectively.
- $\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{III}}$ and $\tau_{\text{sat}}^{\text{IV}}$ the saturation flow stress associated with stage III and stage IV, respectively.

Eq. (5) can be transformed into a flow curve by using the Taylor factor, see Coppieters et al. (2019) for more details. The two-stage strain hardening model is fitted to the same pre-necking tensile data as shown by the black solid curve in **Figure 3**. Due to the increased flexibility, the two-stage Voce model perfectly captures the strain hardening up to maximum uniform tensile strain. The fitting process yields also a value for the transition point between stage III and stage IV hardening. This value is merely a fitting result and has no physical meaning whatsoever. It is rather questionable that stage IV is activated in the pre-necking region of a tensile test (Vegter et al., 2016). The two-stage Voce model is merely used as a phenomenological model giving excellent accuracy for technological applications. Due to different micro-mechanical mechanisms, the large strain flow curve is a composite curve. Other equations that are in line with the phenomenological nature of large strain work hardening can be proposed, e.g. linear combinations of existing hardening laws as proposed by for example Sung et al. (2010).

Figure 3. Fitting quality of the Voce model (Eq. (4)) and a Two-stage Voce model (Eq. (5)) for a low carbon steel sheet, after Coppieters et al. (2019).

Although the two-stage Voce model accurately captures the pre-necking strain hardening as

well as the rate of strain hardening at maximum uniform tensile strain, one cannot guarantee that the extrapolation of this two-stage Voce model is valid. Moreover, despite the physics behind the Voce-based hardening models, a pure phenomenological model often yields good results. A myriad of hardening laws is available in the literature, but in the majority of the studies adopting those hardening laws the validated strain range is derived from pre-necking strain hardening data. For the post-necking regime, one cannot easily assign the most appropriate hardening law for a material without having access to experimental data. The reason is twofold. First, post-necking data are not widely available as it requires dedicated experiments. Second, the commonly adopted hardening laws were not devised to describe the post-necking regime of sheet metal.

Figure 4a shows a schematic large strain flow curve of a single-phase metal as deduced from experimental data acquired by Gil Sevillano et al. (1980). Gil Sevillano et al. reported that BCC metals and alloys show a linear behaviour up to very large plastic deformations, except in the case of torsion leading to saturation of the flow stress. Based on this observation, Gil Sevillano et al. proposed the saturation of the flow curve as shown in **Figure 4a**. **Figure 4b** shows the large strain flow curve in the same strain range as panel (a) measured using the grooved in-plane torsion test on DC04 (Traphöner et al., 2021). For BCC metals, it can be seen that the large strain work hardening can be represented by a constant work-hardening rate (**Figure 4b**). This is also confirmed by the results shown in **Figure 4c** showing a recent result on a dual phase steel sheet (Kolpak et al., (2021)). Kolpak et al. constructed the large strain flow curve using the sheet extrusion test. With regard to the transition between stage III and stage IV hardening, it can be observed that the experimental flow curves exhibit a similar tendency, i.e. the upside bending of the curve due to entering stage IV hardening. The transition seems to take place around $\bar{\epsilon}_p = 1$. Such a flow curve is clearly more complex than the behaviour described by commonly applied phenomenological hardening laws. Understanding the underlying mechanisms that are responsible for the observed stage-IV hardening (van Liempt, 1994) could lead to improved large strain hardening models, either pure phenomenological in nature, or micro-mechanically informed as proposed by Vegter et al. (2016). In any case, methods are required to probe large strains in sheet metal. In the next section, an overview of the experimental methods adopted in this work is given.

Figure 4. (a) Schematic large strain flow curve for single phase metals (b) Large strain flow curve of a low carbon steel (DC04) measured using the in-plane torsion test (Traphöner et al., 2021) (c) The large strain flow curve of a high strength steel sheet measured using the sheet extrusion test (Kolpak et al., 2021).

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

In addition to the uniaxial tensile test, five testing methods to probe large strain response of sheet metals are compared in this work. They fall in either *Category 1* or *Category 3*, according to the classification proposed in the Introduction.

3.1 Category 1 testing methods

a. In-plane torsion test (IPTT)

The in-plane torsion test (IPTT) was introduced by Marciniak to characterize the flow curve, the Bauschinger effect (Marciniak, 1961) and the fracture strain (Marciniak and Kolodziejcki, 1972). The deformation state is analytically and numerically analysed by Sowerby et al. (1977). Tekkaya et al. (1982) determined flow curves with equivalent strains up to 1.0 and investigated the process limits. Bauer (1987) developed a theoretical description of instability due to wrinkling. Later developments, such as the application of digital image correlation (DIC) for measuring the strains (Yin, 2014) led to a wide range of applications of the IPTT. Advanced specimen shapes and test methods were developed to characterize planar sheets, bulk materials and sheet metal components such as tubes or bulged sheets (Traphöner et al., 2018a). Recent investigations are e.g. about the characterization of the planar anisotropy (Grolleau et al., 2019) and the application of the test for different temperatures and strain rates. Also Wagner et al. (2019) studied the utilization of the in-plane torsion test in industrial applications. Today, there is a large number of publications in which the measurements obtained by the in-plane torsion test are used.

In the classical in-plane torsion test, a sheet metal specimen is clamped between the circular inner clamping with the radius r_I and the ring-shaped outer clamping with the radius r_O , as shown in **Figure 5**. The clamping is realized by applying a clamping force to the inner ($F_{C,I}$)

and the outer clamping ($F_{C,O}$). The applied torque M causes a twisting α between the two clamping jaws leading to elastic and elastic-plastic deformations in the specimen.

Figure 5. In-plane torsion test: (a) Forces, dimensions and (b) deformations.

The torque M resulting the torsion in the sheet plane depends on the rotation (twisting) angle α and is measured by a torque sensor. The shear stress induced by this torque in the specimen at any radius r , assuming isotropic material behaviour, can be calculated by

$$\tau = \frac{M}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot t \cdot r^2}, \quad (6)$$

where t is the sheet thickness of the specimen at the corresponding radius r . The shear stress is assumed to be constant over the entire circumference, and decreases reciprocally with the square of the increasing radius. The maximum stress occurs directly at the inner clamping. The deformation of a specimen after the experiment can be illustrated through the deformation of a material line on the specimen surface, which was radially straight before the deformation (**Figure 5b**). The engineering shear strain γ is determined from the change in the slope of this radial line or with the shear angle η by:

$$\gamma = \tan(\eta) = r \frac{d\alpha}{dr}. \quad (7)$$

Equivalent stresses and strains are given by Hill'48-yield criterion as:

$$\sigma_f = \sqrt{3} \tau \sqrt{\frac{2(2r_n+1)}{3(2r_n+1)}} \text{ and } \bar{\epsilon}_p = \frac{\gamma}{\sqrt{3}} \sqrt{\frac{3(2r_n+1)}{2(2r_n+1)}} \quad (8)$$

where r_n is the normal anisotropy parameter. In most investigations the stresses (and depending on the evaluation method also the strains) are averaged over the circumference during the experiment. Recently, Grolleau et al. (2022) also investigated the influence of planar anisotropy in the in-plane torsion test. One principal discussion is about the stress and strain state, since the in-plane torsion test achieves equivalent plastic strains above 3.0 (Traphöner et al., 2021). Numerical simulations by Sowerby et al. (1977) showed radial and tangential normal stresses and strains. Experimental results from Bauer (1989) confirmed small (negligible) radial strains. Cwiekala et al. (2022) showed with an analytical model of the in-plane torsion test that the influence of the co-existing radial and circumferential stresses have a negligible influence on the computation of the flow curve.

Tekkaya et al. (1982) analysed the process window for an aluminum alloy Al 98.7w (**Figure 6**). The process window is defined by three boundaries. The first boundary is the sticking limit, where the necessary torque can no longer be transmitted through the clamping surfaces and the material slips under the clampings. The second limiting factor is the maximum torque that can be applied and withstood by the testing machine. The third process limit is buckling due to elastic and elastic-plastic instability. Buckling occurs for small sheet thicknesses and large clamping radii.

Figure 6. Process limits sticking, buckling and maximum allowed torque according to Tekkaya et al. (1982).

The achievable strain using classical planar specimen is limited due to the mechanical imprints of the inner clamping. The pyramidal or linear imprints of the punch surface structure in the material lead to premature failure of the material. Bauer (1987) and Yin (2014) also show that the inner clamps influence the stress state near the inner clamps. Because of the high clamping forces compressive stresses are superposed with the shear stresses. Yin (2014) also shows that the optical strain measurement is not capable to measure the strains directly at the edge of the inner clamp, although, this is where the highest strains occur. For these reasons, it is not possible to determine test data up to the shear fracture strain of the material with the planar specimen.

In order to avoid the influences of clamping, Gese et al. (2002) suggested an abrupt groove of a sharp rectangular shape. However, the measurement of the shear strain in this application is not accurate. Yin (2014) modified the in-plane torsion test specimen with a smooth circumferential groove (**Figure 7**). They accurately measured the shear strains by DIC. The symmetrical reduction in the cross section of the specimen causes the highest shear stress and shear strain to occur close to the root of the groove. The specimen fractures at the radius of maximum deformation in the groove. In addition to the circular groove with constant groove radius r_{groove} shown in **Figure 7**, various improved groove contours have been developed, for example, to prevent the localization of strain (Traphöner et al., 2021).

Figure 7. Principle and characteristic dimensions of specimens with circular groove contour (Yin, 2014).

Basically, specimens with circumferential groove are well suited for the flow curve characterization up to the fracture of the specimen. The achievable fracture strain is, however, significantly dependent on the method used to manufacture the groove (Traphöner et al., 2018b). **Figure 8** shows the fracture strain for the high-strength dual-phase steel DP1000. Grooves with

circular contour were manufactured by turning, milling, electro discharge machining (EDM) and pulsed electro-chemical machining (PECM). Figure 8 shows that a good surface quality corresponds to the highest fracture strains of the specimens.

Figure 8. Fracture strains for DP1000 specimens with circular groove manufactured by turning, milling, EDM and PECM in different surface qualities (Trophöner et al., 2018b).

Figure 9 shows setup of the in-plane torsion test, which is used for the studies at TU Dortmund University. The torsion test is mounted into a universal uniaxial testing machine. A servomotor with two-stage gearing drives the outer clamp.

Figure 9. In-plane torsion test (IPTT) setup.

The bevel gear of the first stage has a transmission ratio i_1 of 29:1 and the worm gear of the second stage, which drives the external clamping, has a ratio i_2 of 376.88:1. The total gear ratio i is thus 10929.52:1, which results in a maximum torsion speed of 98.81 °/min at a maximum motor speed n of 3000 rpm. The rotation test speed is 2 °/min. The inner clamp is rigidly connected to the testing machine. At the center of the sample, an internal clamping force $F_{C,I}$ of 100 kN is applied. With the inner clamping radius r_1 of 15 mm, the internal clamping pressure is approx. 140 MPa. For the outer clamping, a connection of eight screws is used to provide the outer clamping force $F_{C,O}$. The relative rotation α angle is measured using an incremental rotation angle sensor with an accuracy of 0.01°. The torque M is measured with a torque sensor connected to the outer clamping-ring. An optical strain measurement system is used to measure the local strains on the specimen. The measurement distance is 230 mm and the resulting strain reference length l_0 is 0.2 mm.

b. Strain-rate controlled hydraulic bulge test (HBT)

The strain rate-controlled hydraulic bulge test (HBT) is effective to determine the stress-strain curve of a sheet metal in a strain range that is larger than that reached in a conventional tensile

test. The HBT is conducted by clamping a circular sheet blank along its periphery and subjecting it by a hydraulic pressure, as shown in **Figure 10**. The hoop stress σ_b at the apex of the specimen is given by

$$\sigma_b = \rho p / (2t) \quad (9)$$

where p is the oil pressure, ρ and t are the radius of curvature and current thickness at the apex of the bulging specimen, respectively. Applying the von Mises material model implies that $\sigma_f = \sigma_b$ while $\bar{\varepsilon}_p = |\varepsilon_{zz}^{pl}|$ with ε_{zz}^{pl} the plastic thickness strain at the apex.

The stress and strain in a bulging specimen are not uniform. Therefore, the gauge length used for calculating the strain and the curvature at the apex should be sufficiently small compared to the diameter of the die cavity. ISO 16808 (2014) specifies the geometry of the die, and r_ρ and r_ε as follows:

$$D/t_0 \geq 33$$

$$5t_0 \leq r_d \leq 15t_0 \quad (r_d: \text{radius of die lip, maximum 15 mm})$$

$$r_\rho = (0.125 \pm 0.025) \times D$$

$$r_\varepsilon = (0.05 \pm 0.01) \times D \quad (10)$$

Figure 10. Schematic of hydraulic bulge test (ISO 16808, 2014). r_ρ is the surface radius, ρ the radius of curvature, r_ε is the surface radius, and t_0 is the initial thickness of the blank.

For a HBT equipped with mechanical devices to measure r_ε and ρ , Yoshida (2013) performed FE simulations to show that the accuracy of the stress measurement for an isotropic sheet material is estimated to be within 1% under the following conditions:

- (i) Evaluation of the meridional strain at the mid layer.
- (ii) Estimation of the meridional stress through the internal pressure.
- (iii) The experimental set up complies with $\frac{R\rho}{D} \leq 0.1$, $\frac{R\varepsilon}{D} \leq 0.05$, and $\frac{t_0}{D} \leq 0.01$. With $2R_\rho$ the initial opening of spherometer used to measure ρ , and $2R_\varepsilon$ is the initial gauge length used to determine the meridional strain.

The stress state at the apex deviates from the equibiaxial stress state ($\frac{\sigma_{xx}}{\sigma_{yy}} = 1$) for plastically orthotropic material. Yoshida (2013) found that this depends on the level of plastic anisotropy, yet complies with $1.01 < \frac{\sigma_{yy}}{\sigma_{xx}} < 1.05$, provided that σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} are aligned with the RD and TD, respectively.

In order to accurately measure the equibiaxial stress-strain curves of anisotropic sheet metals, the biaxial tensile stress test using a cruciform specimen (ISO 16842, 2014) or the multiaxial tube expansion test (MTET) should be used. The former is effective for the measurement of the biaxial deformation behavior of sheet metals in a strain range of several percent or less. For a larger strain range the MTET is effective, in which servo-controlled axial force and internal pressure are applied to a cylindrical test piece made from a sheet sample to generate a biaxial stress state. Kuwabara and Sugawara (2013) investigated the differential hardening behavior of a mild steel using the cruciform test and the MTET. Hakoyama and Kuwabara (2015) applied an optical 3D deformation analysis system to the MTET apparatus to measure the forming limit strains and stresses of a precipitation hardening steel sheet with a tensile strength of 590 MPa.

Figure 11 shows the directions of the plastic strain rates, β , measured using the HBT and MTET for a 590 MPa precipitation hardening high strength steel sheet. In the MTET linear stress paths with the true stress ratios, $\sigma_x : \sigma_y$, chosen to be 4:1, 2:1, 4:3, 1:1, 3:4, 1:2, and 1:4, were applied to the test material, and β was measured using an optical strain measurement system. It is noted that $\beta \approx 45^\circ$ for the HBT while $30^\circ \leq \beta \leq 38^\circ$ for the test of $\sigma_x : \sigma_y = 1:1$ in the MTET. This is experimental evidence that the stress ratio at the apex of the HBT specimen deviates from equibiaxial tension.

Figure 11. Measured directions of the plastic strain rates using HBT and MTET (Hakoyama et al., 2013). Material: 590 MPa precipitation hardening high strength steel sheet. ϵ_0^p is the uniaxial plastic strain in the RD tensile test, representing the level of plastic work per unit volume consumed during each linear stress path test. β is the direction of the plastic strain rate, defined to be 0 when parallel to the RD and positive in the anticlockwise direction.

Ranta-Eskola (1979) suggested that the strain rate needs to be constant for an accurate measurement of biaxial stress-strain curves. **Figure 12** shows a feedback control circuit for keeping the strain rate constant. The computer outputs reference strain data at a constant rate. Then, the data are compared with those measured using a DIC strain measurement system. The difference in the reference and measured strain data activates the servo valve to control the pressure of the HBT apparatus.

Readers can find excellent reviews on the hydraulic bulge test method in Yoshida (2013) and Mulder et al. (2015). A mechanical device for measuring the biaxial strains at the apex was developed by Johnson and Ducan (1965). Gologranc (1975) and Young et al. (1981) have developed automated hydraulic bulge testers. Keller et al. (2009) developed an optical system to directly measure the biaxial flow curve. Mulder et al. (2015) evaluated the validity of the testing procedures adopted in ISO 16808. Min et al. (2017) proposed a novel strategy for improving the accuracy for isotropic and orthotropic sheet materials by considering several effects including bending and elastic volume change. In comparison with ISO 16808, accounting for these effects significantly improves the accuracy for determining the stress state at the apex. Finally,

it should be mentioned that strain-rate controlled hydraulic bulge test serves as an excellent experimental validation to assess the predictive accuracy of material models. For example, Yanaga et al. (2012) used the hydraulic bulge test to experimentally validate the material modeling of 6000 series aluminum alloy sheets with different density cube textures.

Figure 12. Feedback control circuit for keeping strain rate constant during the hydraulic bulge test (HBT).

c. Plane strain compression test (PSCT)

The PSCT is a quasi-homogeneous material testing procedure mentioned in the scientific literature since the early 1950's. A rectangular sample of the sheet metal to test is subjected to through-thickness compression between two dies, as shown in **Figure 13**. The dies are larger than the sheet width b , while their width w must be chosen so that plane strain conditions are reached during the test. For that, Loveday et al. (2006) suggested that the ratio h_0/w should be larger than 0.25 and smaller than 0.5 ... 1, while the sheet width b_0 should be larger than 5 ... 6 times the tool width w . The same values were confirmed a decade later by Aksenov et al. (2015), among other authors.

Figure 13. Plane strain compression test (PSCT) configuration at the beginning (left) and at the end (right) of the test (Gelin et al., 1994).

The popularity of the plane strain compression test, in particular for rolling applications, is due to a number of advantages:

- The testing equipment is very simple; a universal tension-compression machine is required, along with two compression dies of rectangular cross-section. A simple rectangular sample is required.
- The stress field as well as the strain field are supposed sufficiently homogeneous for the flow curve to be determined analytically based on the load and die displacement measurements. In particular, no local strain measurement technique is required.
- The loading mode induced in the material is similar to that encountered during flat rolling (Pietrzyk et al., 1993) thus offering a material characterization particularly suitable for this particular forming process.
- The resulting force-stroke curve exhibits a very good repeatability.
- The test, although not standardized, is well documented, see for example Kowalski et al. (2003).
- Finally, the compressive loading mode allows for significantly larger strains prior to failure, compared to the tensile test.

The main application of the plane strain compression test was for material characterization in the context of hot rolling. However, Kubié and Delamare (1980) applied the test for the characterization of sheet metal at room temperature, and the resulting flow curves were used for various applications. The cumulated strain during the test is based on the plane strain assumption, making use of the thickness strain component $\varepsilon_{zz} = \ln(h/h_0)$ and a selected yield surface model; all authors agree on this strain calculation approach. In turn, the flow stress calculation is significantly more involved. Indeed, the strain and stress fields are not homogeneous due to the presence of friction, even when good lubrication conditions are applied as shown by Aksenov et al. (2015). The slab method is used to account for the influence of friction. Becker et al. (1989) used the Coulomb friction model, Kubié and Delamare (1980) adopted the Tresca friction model and Loveday et al. (2006) used the Coulomb-Tresca friction model. Similar results were obtained with the different friction models, provided that the friction coefficient is known with sufficient accuracy. Actually, all authors recommend optimized lubrication to be applied. At room temperature, Becker et al. (1989) found that the use of Teflon sheets and grease leads to friction coefficients between 0.02 and 0.07. Mirza and Sellars (2001) used FE-based methods to determine the influence of friction. Kubié and Delamare (1980) used compression dies of different widths to characterize the influence of friction. Becker et al. (1989) and Aksenov et al. (2015) proposed additional corrections in order to account for the shear strain induced at the edge of the tool and the increase of the sample width b during the test, respectively. Finally, Chermette et al. (2020) calculated the flow stress with the following expression:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{F}{wb} \frac{1}{\frac{h}{\mu w} \left(\exp\left(\mu \frac{w}{h}\right) - 1 \right) + \frac{1}{4} \tan(\alpha)} \quad (11)$$

where F is the compression load, w and b are the widths of the tool and sample, respectively, and μ is the friction coefficient (in this case, Coulomb friction is assumed). Angle α is the angle of the free surface at the tool edge, as shown in **Figure 14**, which can be rigorously determined as a function of h on geometrical basis.

Figure 14. Definition of the lateral extrusion angle α used in the shear correction term of Eq. (11) (Chermette et al., 2020).

FE simulations have been used to emphasize these heterogeneity sources. Pietrzyk et al. (1993) and Gelin et al. (1994) constructed numerical-experimental inverse methods for the parameter identification of flow curve models using the PSCT. On the other hand, such FE simulations also served to verify that the analytical Eq. (11) describes the flow curve with very good accuracy, without relying on any pre-defined hardening model.

From an experimental viewpoint, Semiatin and Altan (2010) described several weaknesses of the PSCT, among which the stress concentration at the tool corner, which can induce early fracture in the material, as well as possible errors due to a misalignment between the two dies, given the relatively small die width. An appealing solution to both problems was proposed by Becker et al. (1989) who used compression dies with rounded edges. Chermette et al. (2020) proved with FE simulations that when using dies with rounded edges, the stress and strain field heterogeneities are significantly reduced with respect to the case of sharp edges, and the impact of tool misalignment is also reduced. Nevertheless, with rounded tools the effective width of the compression area is variable and needs to be calculated accordingly.

Recently, Chermette et al. (2020) have thoroughly and critically investigated the PSCT and applied it to twenty sheet steel materials with a range of ultimate tensile strength between 472 and 1533 MPa and thicknesses between 0.8 and 3.1 mm. A very good accuracy of the PSCT procedure was observed. In particular, for ten materials the predicted flow curve could be compared to that obtained from hydraulic bulge tests, and a relative accuracy of $\pm 2\%$ between the two tests was observed. For a consistent comparison with the hydraulic bulge test, the PSCT flow curves were adjusted with respect to an additional tensile experiment. This recently proposed correction significantly improves the accuracy and robustness of the resulting flow curve, given that the plane strain compression test, just like the hydraulic bulge test, provides less

accurate results in the small strain range. Since both the tensile test and the plane strain compression test are performed so that the main metal flow direction is in the rolling direction (Rees, 2012) these final correction factors are in most cases very close to unity.

d. Stack compression test (SCT)

The Stack compression test (SCT) enables to probe large plastic strains by to suppressing plastic instabilities in sheet metal. To the authors best knowledge, Tozawa and Nakamura (1967) conducted the first SCT on sheet metal. Small circular discs (Merklein and Kuppert, 2009) or square specimens (An and Vegter, 2005) can be used to form the stack. Compression testing of metallic materials is described in DIN 50106 recommending a height to width ratio of one or higher to mitigate the effect of friction. However, a small aspect ratio (i.e. height to diameter ratio) is preferred to attain a large reduction of the stack. An and Vegter (2005) showed that for a small aspect ratio, frictional effects need to be compensated. Irrespective of the method to do so, this friction force compensation implies that the frictional condition can be determined. Generally, the compensation method relies on a constant frictional condition. Yet, frictional conditions vary as lubrication depletes during the test. In this regard, An and Vegter (2005) have reported that a constant frictional behavior can be obtained using oiled PTFE film. A recent study of Kraus et al. (2021) shows that the frictional condition can indeed change during a compression test on a single disc. However, it is shown that for DP600 used in this study, the friction coefficient tends to converge with an increasing contact pressure. Consequently, Kraus et al. (2021) concluded that a constant friction coefficient of 0.078 is sufficiently accurate to represent the tribological conditions of DP600 during the compression test. Based on the individual disc thickness after compression, Coppieters et al. (2020) inversely identified the friction coefficient using a SCT on DP600. A friction coefficient of 0.05 was found. Given the different test conditions (stack configuration, lubricant and level of stack reduction), the latter value is in good agreement with the work of Kraus et al. (2021). Lenzen et al. (2021) recently proposed the pin extrusion test to characterize the frictional condition required for analytical compensation of the friction influence in the SCT. Koizumi and Kuroda (2018) developed a stack compression test method with a strong focus on reducing the friction. To this end, they used compression platens coated with a 1-mm-thick sintered polycrystalline diamond (PCD) layer. Koizumi and Kuroda concluded that for a mild steels sheet, the flow stress in compression is clearly higher than in tension. Using Koizumi and Kuroda's testing method, Kuwabara et al. (2022) adopted a two-specimen approach to eliminate the effect of elastic deformation of the experimental set up and remaining frictional effects (if any). Carefully conducted experiments on a

low carbon steel sheet revealed a consistent discrepancy between the SCT and the HBT, which requires further study, yet pointed in the direction of a dependency of flow stress on the hydrostatic pressure.

The experimental details of the stack compression test used in Section 4 are described in Coppieters et al. (2020). The equivalent strain is calculated as the logarithmic true compressive strain:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_p = \ln \left(\frac{h_0}{h} \right). \quad (12)$$

Alves et al. (2011) found that a stacked cylinder yields identical results to that of solid cylinder specimens. However, for small aspect ratio (in this study: 3 discs of diameter 10 mm) it is required to compensate for friction. The friction-hill analysis for the homogenous compression of a single disc (Dieter, 1987) leads to:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{2 \cdot \sigma_{\text{avg}}^c}{\left(\frac{h}{\mu r} \right)^2 \cdot \left[e^{\frac{2\mu r}{h}} - \frac{2\mu r}{h} - 1 \right]} \quad (13)$$

with the current height h , the current radius r of the stack and the coefficient of friction μ . The average compressive stress σ_{avg}^c is computed as:

$$\sigma_{\text{avg}}^c = \frac{F \cdot h}{\pi \cdot r_0^2 \cdot h_0} \quad (14)$$

with F the measured force and h_0, r_0 the initial stack height and radius, respectively.

3.2 Category 3 testing methods

a. Post-necking tensile experiment (PNTE)

Several methods attempt to exploit the diffuse neck to extend the validity of the standard tensile test. This is driven by the observation that many ductile materials show a significant post-necking region (manifested by diffuse necking) which is usually discarded in post-processing the experimental data. Given the strong trend towards digitization, such significant data loss is unacceptable and therefore is deemed relevant to, instead of discarding the data, fully exploiting the available data. After reaching the maximum tensile load, deformation ceases to be uniform and a diffuse neck develops. **Figure 15a** shows such an experimentally measured diffuse neck in DC05. **Figure 15b** shows the longitudinal Euler-Almansi strain along the necked cross section, the so-called Highest Strained Section (HSS). It can be inferred that the strain field is inhomogeneous across the HSS. Moreover, the deformation progressively localizes. **Figure 15c**

shows the strain evolution within and outside the diffuse neck. Once diffuse necking starts, it can be observed that the deformation outside the necking area stabilizes (and once the load drops, is experiencing elastic spring back). Due to this strain localization, the strain rate within the diffuse neck increases. As shown by Ghosh (1977), a positive strain rate sensitivity enhances the capability of the material to uniformly distribute the strain field within the diffuse neck. The material state within the diffuse neck progressively changes from uniaxial tension towards plane strain tension when localized necking starts. In other words, the material within the diffuse neck is subjected to non-proportional loading. **Figure 16a** shows the strain paths of different material points within the diffuse neck shown in **Figure 15a**. Clearly, the onset of diffuse necking is the start of non-linear straining within the diffuse neck. In the centre of the diffuse neck, the deformation mode gradually evolves towards a plane strain condition as indicated in the figure. This non-proportional loading can also be represented in stress space as schematically shown in the right panel of **Figure 16b**. It can be seen that a transverse stress component (σ_2) is appearing when diffuse necking starts. Tardif and Kyriakides (2012) have shown with the aid of numerical simulations that the development of the transverse stresses is somewhat postponed in ductile sheet metal. In this regard, Iadicola (2011) provided experimental evidence by simultaneously measuring the stress and strain using DIC and X-ray diffraction, respectively, during diffuse necking. In fact, the development of a transverse stress component turns out to be a driving factor for post-uniform elongation. Indeed, Hora et al. (2013) found that the transverse stress component activates an additional strain hardening effect. The latter effect obviously depends on the plastic anisotropy of the material as this determines the magnitude of the transverse stress component. This insight was already provided in the early work of Ghosh (1977) who clearly showed that the post-uniform elongation of metals scales with the planar anisotropy r . A large r value corresponds with an elongated yield surface along equibiaxial tension direction, hence a large transverse stress component, and, as a consequence, leads to a large additional strain hardening effect that postpones local necking.

Figure 15. (a) Diffuse neck (b) Strain distribution along the HSS (c) and Strain evolution inside and outside the diffuse neck.

Figure 16. (a) Strain paths of different material points within the diffuse neck shown in **Figure 15** and (b) nonproportional loading in stress space during diffuse necking (after Hora et al. (2013)).

Pioneering work of Bridgman (1952) resulted in a methodology to account for the distribution of the stress and the strain across the diffuse neck. Bridgman considered his approach (*Category I*) as a second approximation of the problem: “*A complete solution here would demand a specification of the stress and the strain at all points in the plastically flowing tension specimen, and in particular would involve a complete determination of the contour of the specimen at points remote from the neck as well as in the neighborhood of the neck*” (Bridgman, 1952). Although Bridgman made some efforts in this direction by measuring the contours of the necking profiles, he was fully aware of the strong assumptions. While Bridgman-like second approximations, e.g. as proposed Davidenkov and Spiridonova (1946), turned out to be valid for cylindrical tensile specimen, Aronofsky (1951) showed that the geometry of the diffuse neck for flat specimen is much more complex. The analytical compensation requires the following strong assumptions:

1. The profile of the diffuse neck approximates the arc of a circle;
2. A state of plane strain prevails across the diffuse neck;
3. Plastically isotropic material behavior is assumed.

The above assumptions are deemed questionable for sheet metal. Interestingly, the first “complete solution” was presented by Ghosh (1977). Ghosh measured the strain inhomogeneity across the diffuse neck using the grid method. The strain increments in each grid element were used to reconstruct the stress component in the tensile direction assuming plane stress, planar and normal anisotropy. The material behaviour was modelled using Hill’s quadratic yield criterion, the modified Levy-Mises flow rule and isotropic hardening. The total tensile force was computed by summation of the reconstructed stress components. However, the actual goal of Gosh was to study the influence of the hardening parameters and r -value on the flow curve. Nevertheless, the work of Gosh was a huge step forward towards the complete solution envisioned by Bridgman. Indeed, Saka et al. (1979) showed that with some minor modifications the approach of Ghosh could be used to identify the change of the hardening exponent n when entering the post-uniform region. Ayres (1983) adopted the same approach but argued that Saka’s approach of isolating the central element in the diffuse neck was inherently inaccurate. Instead, Ayres (1983) evaluated the strain hardening over the entire cross section. Similar to Saka’s intention, Ayres aimed at evaluating the accuracy rather than the identification of the hardening law. Unfortunately, the work of Saka and Ayres was not recognized as a strong step forward in extracting the working hardening from the diffuse neck. As finite element codes

reached a sufficient level of accuracy, however, several researchers embarked on numerical studies to derive analytical approaches to compensate for diffuse necking, much in the spirit of Bridgman's correction method. For example, Zhang et al. (1999) proposed an area reduction equation which takes the non-proportional area reduction during diffuse necking into account. The second approximation definitely contributed to the understanding of the problem of post-necking hardening phenomena, but it is now understood that only considering the conditions at the HSS is potentially inaccurate.

Full-field measuring techniques emerged two decades after the work of Ghosh (1977) sparking the development of complete solutions to identify the working hardening during diffuse necking. The most intuitive inverse approach is the so-called Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) technique. The opportunity to identify the strain hardening behaviour from the diffuse neck using FEMU was simultaneously recognized by numerous research teams. Koc and Štok (2004) used FEMU and the load-elongation curve. However, inverse methods based on the global response of diffuse necking (e.g. a load-elongation curve) do not explicitly account for the necking profile and strain field. Gorji et al. (2016) showed that the post-necking material response is prone to geometrical material inhomogeneity's. Starman et al. (2019) found that the scatter of material properties, loading conditions and geometric imperfections have a strong effect on the load-elongation curve. An important caveat, however, is that Starman et al. found that diffuse necking is a deterministic process. Indeed, after the start of diffuse necking, the force decreases with a deterministic slope. A number of researchers started to use local information acquired using full-field measurement techniques. For example, Scheider et al. (2004) proposed to use the load-width curve, where the minimum width of the diffuse neck was measured using DIC, to derive an empirical correction factor. Wang and Tong (2015) derived a correction factor via numerical simulations to account for non-symmetric and irregular neck morphologies. Dunand and Mohr (2010) used local strain measurements with the diffuse neck to feed the FEMU approach. The latter approach was proposed to cope with the difficulty of using full field displacement data as proposed by Kajberg and Lindkvist (2004) and later by Pottier et al. (2008). The study of Pottier et al. can be considered as a true complete solution for diffuse necking as it accounts for local and global response, including the specimen's shape and the overall stress levels.

The identified work hardening is deemed to be more accurate when using local strain fields and the necking profile. Despite the innovative character of the work of Kajberg and Lindkvist (2004), the complete solution via FEMU suffers from the following:

1. Modelling the plastic instability using a FE code is not trivial task. For example, the diffuse neck might exhibit mesh dependency;
2. The FE computations are time consuming;
3. A cumbersome coupling between the experiment and the FE Model.

The nonlinear VFM enables to cope with the abovementioned limitations of the FEMU approach. The nonlinear VFM has also been applied to diffuse necking. The work of Coppieters et al. (2011) turned out to belong to the nonlinear VFM, yet using actual fields instead of virtual fields. The procedure proposed by Coppieters et al. (2011) is closely related to early work of Ghosh (1977). The methodology presented by Coppieters et al. (2011) is in essence an energy method: the internal work and external work should be equal provided that quasi-static loading conditions prevail during diffuse necking. The idea of such an inverse energy approach was firstly formulated by Strano and Altan (2004), albeit outside the context of full-field measurements. Strano and Altan (2004) used the energy balance in a quasi-static hydraulic bulge experiment on tubular specimens to calculate the flow stress. Other researchers adopted identical ingredients as used by Coppieters et al. (2011), but confined their analysis to expressing force equilibrium along the HSS in the diffuse neck. Coruk and Karadoğan (2011) proposed to reconstruct the longitudinal stress components along the HSS in the diffuse neck. The flow curve is then identified by seeking force balance between the measured and reconstructed tensile force. Similar approaches for round bar (Majzoobi and Fariba (2014)) and sheet metal (Marth et al. (2016)) were proposed. It can be concluded that the methodology of Coppieters et al. (2011) and Kim et al. (2013) are in very close agreement with the complete solution envisioned by Bridgman (1952). The key point of these methods is that the strain hardening behaviour is determined by stating that the internal work equals the external work in a quasi-static tensile test. The methodology can be explained by focusing on the schematic, simplified diffuse neck shown in **Figure 17**. The speckled area is the Area of Interest (AOI) where the diffuse neck is developing. In this AOI, the internal work will be calculated and reads as:

$$W_{\text{int}} = \int_V \left[\int_{\varepsilon_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij} \right] dV \quad (15)$$

where V is the volume, σ_{ij} and ε_{ij} the stress and the strain field, respectively. The free-body diagram of **Figure 17** enables to derive the external work:

$$W_{\text{ext}} = \int_S \left[\int_{u_i} f_i u_i \right] dS \quad (16)$$

where S is the external surface of the volume V . f_i are the surface tractions and u_i is the displacement field associated with S . Provided that the lines A-B and C-D remain straight (no shear stresses will develop along these lines as the test is conducted in the RD), the external work can be computed using the tensile force F and the elongation u of the AOI:

$$W_{\text{ext}} = \int_u F du \quad (17)$$

The calculation of the internal work W_{int} requires two essential ingredients, namely the strain field and the associated stress field.

Figure 17. Schematic, simplified diffuse neck.

Given that the stress field is reconstructed using experimental strain increments, strain field reconstruction is an important step in the identification scheme. This procedure is schematically shown in **Figure 18**. The displacement fields are measured using DIC. A finite element (FE) mesh is afterwards fitted to the measured displacement fields resulting in displacement components in each node of the FE mesh. The latter situation can be seen as a converged step in an FE analysis. Indeed, once the displacements of the nodes are known, the associated deformation gradient and thus strain tensor can be derived in any point within the AOI. Given that several strain fields are available, the strain increment $\Delta \varepsilon_{ij}$ (i.e. the strain increment in a specific material point from one strain field to the next strain field) in every Gauss point is known. This information is used by the stress update algorithm to compute the stress increment and arrive at the reconstructed stress field. Obviously, the stress update algorithm uses the constitutive material model. To this end, two elements are used here: the concept of a plane stress (anisotropic)

yield criterion and its evolution due to work hardening. A finite set of unknown hardening parameters \mathbf{q} are inversely found by minimizing the difference between the internal work W_{int} and the external work W_{ext} using the following cost function:

$$C(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^N [(W_{\text{int}})_i - (W_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{q}))_i]^2 \quad (18)$$

with N the number of experimentally acquired displacement fields. The only constraint with respect to expressing equivalence between internal and external work comes from the upper bound theorem (Lubliner, 2006): when the correct material model is applied, the calculated internal work W_{int} cannot be smaller than the true external work W_{ext} :

$$W_{\text{ext}} \leq W_{\text{int}} \quad (19)$$

As opposed to *Category I tests*, the accuracy of the large strain flow curve obtained by the inverse method depends on the chosen material model, i.e. the hardening law and the (anisotropic) yield criterion. However, in case of the PNTE, an increase of the cost function caused by an error in the work hardening law is significantly larger than an increase by an error in the anisotropic yield criterion (Coppeters and Kuwabara, 2014).

Figure 18. Displacement field after Digital Image Correlation, strain reconstruction and stress reconstruction.

4 Application to a high strength sheet steel

a. Material

The material considered in this paper is a dual-phase (DP) steel for cold forming, namely CR330Y590T-DP (referred to DP600), having a nominal thickness of 1 mm. As shown in **Figure 19**, the test sample features a (soft) ferritic microstructure containing islands of martensite

in the secondary phase. As a result of their microstructure, DP steels exhibit an excellent trade-off between strength and formability. The high strain hardenability enables DP steels to efficiently redistribute strains, which is an important asset in forming applications. **Table 1** reports the mechanical properties of the DP600 steel derived from standard tensile tests (according to ISO 6892-1 (2019) standard) in the RD.

Figure 19. Micrograph of DP600 (scale: 500X). Grain size (ASTM E112): 12.8 (58 – 54 - 60 /x960)

Table 1. Mechanical properties of DP600 measured using standard tensile test (ISO 6892-1, 2019) in the rolling direction (RD). Young's modulus E , proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$, tensile strength R_m , total elongation A_{80} and maximum uniform elongation A_g and anisotropy coefficients.

E in GPa	$\sigma_{0.2}$ in MPa	R_m in MPa	A_{80} (%)	A_g (%)	r_0	r_{45}	r_{90}
206	386	635	24.8	14.2	0.812	0.709	0.988

b. Results and discussion

All test specimens were manufactured from the same batch DP600. Each material test was conducted at least two or three times. Given the low scatter in the acquired experimental data, one representative result per material test is plotted in **Figure 20**. The flow curve through the uniaxial tensile test (UTT) does not correspond with the flow curves resulting from the other material tests assuming plastic isotropy following the von Mises yield criterion. To compensate for the observed plastic anisotropy and its potential evolution during plastic deformation, the

flow curves can be converted to the UTT using the work equivalence principle. The latter approach is described in the ISO 16808 (2014) standard to convert the equibiaxial flow curve determined via the HBT to the UTT in the RD. The same approach is followed by Chermette et al. (2020) to convert the plane strain compression test (PSCT) flow curve to the UTT. **Figure 21** shows the converted large strain flow curves. The principle of work equivalence is used at the maximum uniform tensile strain. The plastic work associated with this point is then used to determine the corresponding stress-strain pair in the considered material test. This enables to compute the conversion factor f :

$$f = \frac{\sigma_{\text{MAT}}^{\text{ref}}}{\sigma_{\text{UTT}}^{\text{ref}}} \quad (20)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{UTT}}^{\text{ref}}$ is the true stress at maximum uniform tensile strain in the RD. $\sigma_{\text{MAT}}^{\text{ref}}$ is the true stress in the considered material test determined by the work equivalence principle. Finally, the converted flow curves are constructed via:

$$\sigma_f' = \frac{\sigma_f}{f} \quad (21)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_p' = f \bar{\varepsilon}_p \quad (22)$$

with σ_f and $\bar{\varepsilon}_p$ the true stress and true plastic strain, respectively, from the considered material test. From the unconverted results shown in **Figure 20**, it can be stated that the flow curves obtained through the IPTT, the PSCT test and the HBT correspond very well to each other. In terms of maximum attainable plastic strain, the in-plane torsion test outperforms all other material tests and enables to probe an equivalent plastic strain of about 0.9. However, it must be noted that Traphöner et al. (2021) found that the in-plane torsion test enables to probe true plastic strains up to 3.2. The plane strain compression test and the hydraulic bulge test enable to probe equivalent plastic strains up to 0.7. It can be observed that the stack compression test deviates significantly from the hydraulic bulge test. Kuwabara et al. (2022) studied this discrepancy and hypothesized that this can be due to an influence of the hydrostatic pressure. However, for bcc materials, this must be further investigated as mechanisms related to the dislocation core structure might also give an explanation for this observation, as suggested by Gröger et al. (2008).

Figure 20. Large strain flow curves of DP600 obtained through post-necking tensile experiment (PNTE), strain-rate controlled hydraulic bulge test (HBT), in-plane torsion test (IPTT), stack compression test (SCT) and plane strain compression test (PSCT). The pre-necking hardening behaviour is measured using the uniaxial tensile test (UTT) in the RD.

Figure 21. Converted large strain flow curves of DP600 obtained through post-necking tensile experiment (PNTE), strain-rate controlled hydraulic bulge test (HBT), in-plane torsion test (IPTT), stack compression test (SCT) and plane strain compression test (PSCT). The pre-necking hardening behaviour is measured using the uniaxial tensile test (UTT) in the RD.

The converted flow curves shown in **Figure 21** show a very good overall correspondence. The conversion of the stack compression test leads to an underestimation of the flow curve up to maximum uniform tensile strain. The plane strain compression test exhibits some upside bending as from a true plastic strain of about 0.65. Although this upside bending resembles the transition between stage II and stage IV hardening, the in-plane torsion test flow curve clearly does not exhibit this behaviour. Therefore, the upside bending of the plane strain compression test flow curve might be related to the effect of hydrostatic pressure or a degradation in the frictional condition. Further research is required here. **Figure 22** shows the hardening rate $\theta = \frac{d\sigma_f}{d\bar{\varepsilon}_p}$ as a function of the plastic equivalent strain. The hardening slope of the plane strain compression test flow curve diverges with respect to the hardening slopes obtained with the hydraulic bulge test and the in-plane torsion test.

The PNTE flow curve does not require any conversion as the experiment is conducted on a tensile specimen in the RD. The identified post-necking strain hardening corresponds very well with the in-plane torsion test and the hydraulic bulge test. However, the accuracy of the PNTE is strongly dependent on the chosen hardening law. The advantage of the PNTE is that the identification takes only seconds. Consequently, many hardening laws can be evaluated and the one yielding the lowest cost function residual is automatically selected. For DP600, the modified Swift hardening law that reads as:

$$\sigma_f = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}_p)^n - A\bar{\varepsilon}_p \quad (23)$$

yielded the lowest cost function residual. The identified hardening parameters are reported in **Table 2**.

Figure 22. Strain hardening rate derived from the converted large strain flow curves of DP600 obtained through strain-rate controlled hydraulic bulge test (HBT), in-plane torsion test (IPTT) and plane strain compression test (PSCT).

Table 2. Parameters of the modified Swift law (Eq. (23)) for DP600 determined using the post-necking tensile experiment (PNTE).

K in MPa	ε_0	n	A in MPa
1143	0.00178	0.21	292

Although the PNTE determines the large strain flow curve up to twice the maximum uniform tensile strain, it must be emphasized that the weak point of the PNTE is that it relies on stress reconstruction driven by an a priori chosen hardening model. The problem here is that the commonly adopted hardening laws are not designed to describe the post-necking hardening behaviour. From a scientific viewpoint, the in-plane torsion test and the plane strain compression test are very interesting experiments to understand the micro-mechanical mechanisms that drive stage-IV hardening. The latter potentially enables to devise more appropriate hardening laws that can be calibrated with less advanced material testing methods, yet enabling reliable extensions to high strain values.

The PNTE flow curve (obtained by the inverse approach presented in Section 3.2) reported in

Figure 20 and **Figure 21** was extracted using the diffuse neck in a JIS13B type tensile specimen. The JIS13B specimen is not designed for the PNTE as diffuse necking might depend on the chosen tensile specimen geometry. **Figure 23** shows a comparison between an identification based on specimens according to ISO 6892 (width 20 mm, parallel length 120 mm) and JIS13B (width 12.5 mm, parallel length 80 mm), respectively. DP600 steel of the same batch was used. It can be inferred that the identified flow curves are almost identical. Slight differences are likely due to a difference in the development of the diffuse neck, see **Figure 24**.

Figure 23. Large strain flow curve of DP600 identified through the post-necking tensile experiment (PNTE): influence of the test standard.

Figure 24. Diffuse neck and von Mises equivalent strain field in DP600 using different tensile test specimens: (a) ISO 6892 (width 20 mm, parallel length 120 mm) and (b) JIS13B (width 12.5 mm, parallel length 80 mm).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides an overview of the state-of-the-art methods to characterize the post-necking strain hardening behaviour of sheet metal. The methods are divided in three categories. The methods in *Category 1* enable to analytically derive the flow curve using measurands recorded during the experiment. The methods in *Category 2* construct the large strain flow curve by subjecting pre-strained samples to the methods from *Category 1*. Finally, *Category 3* relies on the experiments that require numerical post-processing methods to inversely identify a pre-defined hardening law to describe the large strain flow curve. The selected material tests are discussed in detail and applied to a DP600 steel sheet. From an engineering viewpoint, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The converted flow curves obtained via the selected material tests are in good agreement and deemed sufficiently accurate for engineering applications.
- The in-plane torsion test enables to probe the largest plastic strain followed by the plane strain compression test, the hydraulic bulge test, the post-necking tensile experiment, and the stack compression test.
- The experimental effort associated with the post-necking tensile test and the plane strain compression test is lower than the other material tests.

From a scientific viewpoint:

- The in-plane torsion test yields the ground truth for the large strain flow curve. The data obtained with the in-plane torsion test can be used to devise more appropriate hardening laws.
- At large plastic strain, the plane-strain compression test deviates from the in-plane torsion test. It is hypothesized that this is due to the effect of hydrostatic pressure and/or a degradation of the frictional condition, yet further research is required to understand this observation.
- A discrepancy between the stack compression test and the other material tests is observed. The difference is potentially caused by the effect of hydrostatic pressure on the flow stress but further research is required to confirm this.

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